

The Predictive Power Of Sexual Education Practiced By Parents On The Awareness Of Their Students About Sexual Harassment In The Amman Governorate

Abdul Raouf Hamid Al-Yamani

Article Info

Article History

Received:
January 01, 2021

Accepted:
March 26, 2021

Keywords:

Sex Education, Sexual Harassment, Higher Elementary School Students

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4640809

Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the predictive power of sexual education practiced by parents on their students' awareness about sexual harassment in the governorate of the capital, Amman. The study sample consisted of (374) male and female students from grades eight, nine and ten in the University District Education Directorate in the Amman Governorate in Jordan in the second semester of the academic year (2020/2021 AD), and in order to achieve the objectives of the study, two scales were developed: the sexual education scale, and the sexual harassment awareness scale, and acceptable parameters of validity and reliability were achieved for the two study scales, the results of the study revealed that the level of sexual education practiced by parents on their children, students of the higher basic stage in the capital Amman governorate, was average, and the existence of statistically significant differences in the level of sexual education practiced by parents on their children at the higher primary stage due to the gender variable in favor of females, and that the degree of awareness of sexual harassment among students was average, and the absence of statistical differences in the degree of awareness of sexual harassment among students of the higher basic stage due to the variable of gender, and the results showed that sex education has a statistically significant predictive power of the degree of awareness of sexual harassment, as it explained a percentage (58.6%) of the change in awareness of sexual harassment among students of the higher basic stage in Amman. In light of the results of the current study, the researcher recommended providing informational and educational programs specialized in issues of sexual education and sexual harassment aimed at different age groups, especially the adolescence period, and integrating the topics of sexual education and sexual harassment into school curricula, and conducting training programs for parents and families on issues related to sexual education, and conducting various studies for different samples of students.

Introduction

The issue of sex education and sexual harassment is one of the topics that people fear and are too shy to raise in front of their children, and this may be due to the embarrassment, fear, and unknown concepts surrounding this science, which people are afraid to engage in, especially with their children. It remains among the family and social prohibitions, and the children's experience and their resort to unknown and unsafe sources is left to answer their questions about gender issues. In contrast, the life, social and religious sciences have studied this topic and detailed it in its references, this calls for more studies and research to spread awareness about these concepts and principles. We protect our students from the specter of sexual harassment that is silent on the social and family levels through making them aware and educating their parents about it.

As sexual harassment is one of the things that happen in the whole world without exception, and which is still talked about is one of the things that are silent in our Arab societies, where the World Health Organization estimates (WHO, 2017) one in three women has experienced childhood sexual abuse. Since 1980, sexual harassment and its consequences have become a serious issue of international importance (Kantha & Matsui, 2021). And sexual harassment is a widespread phenomenon in educational institutions and public places such as shopping centers, bazaars, and markets (Jamshed & Kamal, 2020). It is a phenomenon that exists even if there are no accurate statistics of the number of people who are subjected to harassment in our countries, and this is for several considerations, including feeling shy, fear of society's view of the child and his family, and fear of the perpetrator sometimes, and this leads to silence of the victim or the entire family, especially if the

perpetrator is close. The cruelty that some parents take to raise their children may cause the child to remain silent about what he is also subjected to for fear of punishment (Shaker, 2012).

Sexual harassment is a symptom of social discrimination when a person becomes the subject of discussion, sexual gestures, or an unwanted sexual act (Jung & Yoon, 2020). Researchers have been exposed to forms of sexual harassment by explaining the concept of this type of violence because some misconceptions have entered into this concept, such as how some view sexual harassment. It is only that which reaches the point of rape or a full practice, forgetting that even a look, words or contact is sexual harassment, where Al-Sayyid (2000) indicated that sexual harassment includes the arousal that a child or girl is intentionally exposed to for viewing explicit scenes or nude sexual images or intentional touching the genitals or urging him/her to touch another person's genitals, teach him bad habits, or direct sexual assault.

Gharib (2010) argues that sexual harassment is sexual intercourse between a child and an adult to satisfy the sexual desires of an adult by using force and control over the child. Sexual violence is included in the term sexual harassment, as (Dosdale & Skarparis, 2020) defined it as a term that covers many serious violent sexual crimes, as it forces or manipulates another person into unwanted sexual activity without his consent.

Many psychological theories have explained the motives for sexual harassment, as the biological theory indicated that the high male sex hormone of the harasser leads him to search for a way to satisfy his need, so he may resort to sexual harassment to satisfy this instinct, as for the analytical theory, it attributes sexual harassment to the painful repressed experiences of the harasser, as harassment is an expression of the psychological struggles that the individual lived in childhood and was not resolved, such as the oedipal conflict in males and the Electra complex in females. Thus, this theory considers that the harasser suffers from a lack of the supreme ego (the conscience) and an imbalance between his personal structures (the "He" and the ego and the higher ego), and he is a captive of the desires of the id. The cognitive theory refers sexual harassment to negative thought patterns, and cognitive distortions for the harasser and illogical justifications that make him have the right to empty his sexual desire through sexual harassment, and cognitive scholars attribute these misconceptions of harassers to previous experiences that they passed through and added them to their cognitive structures, such as having been subjected to sexual harassment or abuse while they were children (Al-Yamani, 2014; Abu Rias, 2006).

Shaker (2012) believes that it is not necessary that signs of violence appear on the child's body in order to know that he was subjected to abuse or harassment, but in cases where there is no witness to what happened, we can understand through some observations, as the child's behavior usually changes. After he was a cheerful child, playing and having fun like any child of his age, he tends towards introversion and may cry for the simplest reasons, and he may appear fear when a specific person or one of the sexes approaches him, whether he is a man or a woman, and he becomes very fearful and wakes up at night because of disturbing dreams, and may scream at night or mumble words that are incomprehensible, and he suffers from a recurrent fever whose source is not physiological, and he may suffer from indigestion problems or an unwillingness to eat, lose his self-confidence, and sometimes it seems as if he is hiding something, as if he feels that he is the cause of something and feels guilty.

Barbo (2003) believes that sexual harassment is one of the most violent types of abuse and violence that a child may be exposed to and that it results in many negative effects that affect the formation of the child's personality, where he appears shy, self-withdrawal, anxiety and tension, sadness, pain, a tendency to isolation, low daily activities, and a low level of social interaction. And the student needs to form a system of concepts about sexual issues and the concepts of sexual harassment and sexual education to be familiar with them, and not to resort to unsafe sources to learn about these topics, or experiment and practice to discover the unknown, as experimentation usually results from interest formed due to lack of understanding or failure to obtain a satisfactory answer, whereas, sex education helps children and adolescents to form a set of values and concepts to guide their sexual behavior (Asiri and Badawood, 2017).

Alshamas (2003) believes that sex is one of the main motives that direct human thinking and behavior, so it is important to cultivate this motivation, in the context of education in general, and sexual education in particular, so that the individual can later control this motivation within the framework of the values and ethical standards prevalent in society. Levin & Hammock (2020) indicated that sex education aims at sex education, teaching adolescents healthy sexual relations, and sexual education about health diseases associated with sexual practices, violence, sexual harassment, and negative psychological effects. Sex Information & Education Council of Canada (2019) sees sexuality and sex education as an important part of the sexual health, socialization, and development of young adolescents in schools. A healthy sex life, as indicated by UNESCO (2009), is an important part of a positive self-image and the ability to maintain healthy relationships. Sex education provides the individual with information and facts related to gender issues and the development of sound sexual attitudes, represented in understanding the role and functions of sex, and methods of directing and satisfying it, so that the individual can behave positively and properly towards sexual situations by social and ethical standards, in a manner that guarantees sound mental health (Atta and Eid, 2012). Alshamas (2003) believes that sex education combines health education and moral education. It is a gradual process that includes

health, educational care, and this places a great responsibility on the family, represented by direct sexual education. For parents, the main role in sex education for their children, and some mistakes may occur, but parents can overcome them if they behave well in different situations, and the important thing is to present good examples and good ability in their sexual life through the family life they live. In the end, sexual education aims to solve sexual problems and provide assistance to child students to reach the age of puberty, free from fear and sexual perversions, then they are provided with a stable ground away from anxiety and fear, and we provide a safe environment for them to discuss various topics and discussions with complete freedom. And the formation of a family reference for the children, especially if they were exposed to cases of sexual harassment from others, and knowing how to act in such cases instead of the children resorting to external sources that may expose them to sexual exploitation.

The study problem and its questions

The phenomenon of sexual harassment is one of the socially silent phenomena, and this study came as an extension of some studies that went in the direction of exposing this silent phenomenon, Bushra (2017) indicated that the forensic unit in Jordan confirmed that it had detected approximately (500) cases annually. In most of them, the perpetrator is from the family, and the majority of those who fall victim to sexual harassment are children. Perhaps sex education is one of the important and major issues that should be taken care of. So that students grow up with knowledge and familiarity with the issues related to the instinct, even if they grow up, they understand sexual issues and know what is permissible and what is prohibited from doing, so they do not rush into temptations, run after desires, stumble into the path of ignorance, and are not easy prey for sexual harassment. This study came based on the recommendations of many studies to examine such topics and scientifically present them to direct the attention of the educational systems towards these topics as stated in the recommendations of the Gamrah study (2013), the study of Alnaqeeb (2017), the study of Gharib and Ibn Shanna (2018), and the study of Al-Jubaylah. Al-Tarif (2017), Badr Al-Din (2019), Al-Hazmi (2019), Lyu, Shen & Hesketh, (2020), (Rodríguez, Osuna, Dios & Amor, 2020), and Jamshed & Kamal, 2020 study, and the study of Kantha & Matsui study (2021). Therefore, in light of the above, this study came to try to reveal the predictive power of sexual education practiced by parents on the awareness of their students' children about sexual harassment in the governorate of the capital, Amman, by answering the following questions:

1. What level of sex education is practiced by parents on their children, students of the higher primary stage in the governorate of the capital, Amman?
2. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the level of sexual education practiced by parents on their children? Amman, students of the upper primary stage in the governorate of the capital, attributed to the children's sex variable?
3. What is the degree of awareness of sexual harassment among students of the upper primary stage in the capital, Amman?
4. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the degree of awareness of sexual harassment among students of the higher primary stage in the governorate of the capital, Amman, due to the variable of children's sex?
5. How predicted is sexual education practiced by parents on awareness of sexual harassment for students in the capital Amman's upper elementary stage?

The importance of the study

The importance of the current study appears in its handling of an important stage, which is the stage of basic education in schools, and what students may be exposed to at this stage in terms of sexual violence and harassment, and It is one of the most severe and dangerous types of violence, and its effects continue throughout life, and the age stage on which this study was conducted is considered the beginnings of adolescence, whose features are that sexual issues and orientation towards the opposite sex explode. Therefore, sexual education and awareness of sexual harassment are among the most important issues adolescents should pay attention to and address. And the fact that the Arab community is reluctant to address and discuss these issues for multiple considerations, especially among females, so this research opens difficult doors. It links them with sex education, which is one of the most important aspects of education that should be spread awareness among members of society and in educational institutions so that the student does not resort to unreliable sources to find out about his sexual issues and answers the questions that constantly preoccupy him, and needs a full answer from reliable authorities such as parents and teachers. The importance of the study appears in the following:

- Enriching theoretical literature and the educational library with an important topic that many people find difficult to address and deal with is sexual harassment and sexual education, which helps researchers and students learn and benefit from this topic.

- Providing the Ministry of Education and local community institutions with information and descriptive data about students' awareness of sexual education and levels of sexual harassment in schools helps them make appropriate decisions in this field.

- It is hoped that this research will open the way for researchers to study this topic and learn the importance of sex education in protecting society and students from sexual harassment.

- It is hoped that the National Curriculum Center and the Ministry of Education will benefit by reconsidering the integration of sex education within the school curriculum and studying the subject from a scientific, educational, religious, and social aspect.

The limits of the study

The study was applied within the following limits:

- **Objective limits:** revealing students' awareness of sexuality education and its relationship to sexual harassment that students are exposed to.

- **Human Limits:** The study was applied to a sample of students of the higher basic stage in the Education Directorate of the University District in the governorate of the Jordanian capital Amman, and grades (eighth, ninth, and tenth) were chosen.

- **Spatial Limits:** The study was applied in the University District Directorate in the capital, Amman, Jordan.

- **Temporal Limits:** The current study was applied in the second semester of the academic year (2020-2021 AD).

Determinants of the study

The generalization of the results of this study is determined in the light of the following:

- The study scales "Scale of Sex Education and Scale of Awareness of Sexual Harassment" have psychometric characteristics represented in honesty and consistency.

- The integrity of the application procedures and the respondents' objectivity of the study sample to the questionnaire.

Conventional and procedural definitions

This study includes the following formal and procedural definitions:

- **Sex education:** "A form of awareness that provides the individual with sound information, knowledge, and experiences related to sexual matters as permitted by his mental and physical development, what qualifies him to reach psychological and social balance in the future of his sexual and reproductive life (Gharib and Abu Shanna, 2018, 387). And sex education is defined procedurally in this study through the degree of individuals of the study sample of students of the higher basic stage on the study tool that was developed for this purpose.

- **Sexual harassment:** It is a behavior that occurs by any sane person in an unwelcome sexual manner, either explicitly or implicitly, and exploiting the individual's need for work, which leads to the creation of an environment characterized by intimidation, hostility, and attack (Kristina, 2009). Procedurally, sexual harassment is defined in this study through the degree of the study sample members of the upper elementary stage students on the study tool that was developed for this purpose.

- **High basic stage students:** They are students of the eighth, ninth and tenth grades, which fall within the upper primary stage in public schools in the University Brigade Directorate in the governorate of the Jordanian capital, Amman.

Previous studies

Studies related to sexual education and sexual harassment, and the relationship between them, were reviewed. The studies were divided into three axes, the first deals with sex education, the second deals with sexual harassment, and the third deals with the relationship between them. Studies were also presented in chronological order from the oldest to the newest, as follows:

1. Sex education studies

Gamrah (2013) conducted a study to uncover the relationship between a mother and her teenage daughter and its implications for girls' sexual education. The research sample included (188) adolescent girls, from families of different social, economic, and cultural levels, from the city of Makkah, a survey questionnaire was applied to them to identify the relationship of the teenage girl with her mother and the mother's role in sex education for her daughter, and he followed the descriptive and analytical approach in this study. The most important results of the study were as follows: The presence of statistically significant differences between the degrees of the sample members in the relationship of the adolescent girl with her mother according to the study variables (marital status, age, education and profession of the mother), and the existence of statistically significant differences between the degrees of the sample in sexual education according to the study variables

(marital status, age, education and profession of the mother), and the presence of a direct correlation between the axes of the questionnaire of the mother's role in sexual education for her daughter and some of the study variables (Mother's age - eMother's education - Mother's work - Girl's age - girl's educational level), and the existence of a direct correlation between the relationship of the teenage girl with her mother and the sexual education of the teenage girl, and that the mother's role in sex education for her daughter is primarily affected by education (82.8%), and the mother's age is followed by (70.1%), the girl's age comes in third place (63.1%), and finally the mother's profession comes in fourth place (58.1%).

Al-Naqeeb (2017) conducted a study aimed at proposing a model for sex education in kindergarten institutions in Egypt that includes the requirements of sex education in the age group (5-7) years, where the guide includes the following: What is sex education in kindergartens, the philosophy on which the guide is based, the aim of the guide, the requirements of sex education in the age group of (5-7) years, and a pictorial translation of the requirements of sex education in the age group of 5-7 years, and how the teacher uses it.

The study of Asiri and Badoud (2017) aimed to identify parents' attitudes towards providing sex education to their kindergarten children in Riyadh. The research used the descriptive-analytical method. The research group consisted of (248) fathers and mothers of their children enrolled in governmental and private kindergartens in Riyadh. The search tool consisted of a questionnaire to identify parents' attitudes towards providing sex education to their children at kindergarten age in the city of Riyadh, and it included two axes, namely: (Parents' attitudes towards providing sexual education to their children at home, and parents' tendency towards providing sexual education for their children in kindergarten). The research results indicated that fathers and mothers have positive trends towards providing sexual education for their children at home. The results also revealed that parents are not sure of providing sex education to their children in kindergarten. The results also indicated no difference between parents' attitudes regarding (the extent of providing sex education in the home and the extent of providing sex education in kindergarten). And that the educational level has positively affected the attitudes of fathers and mothers about providing sex education to their children at home. In contrast, the educational level did not affect fathers and mothers' attitudes about providing sexual education in kindergarten, and the age variable did not affect the attitudes of fathers and mothers.

The study of Gharib and Ibn Shanna (2018) aimed to identify intermediate education teachers' professional trends towards teaching sex education at this stage. (121) teachers, both males and females, who teach middle school students in the city of Djelfa, Algeria, were selected, and the questionnaire was used to collect information. The results of the study showed that there are positive trends among intermediate education teachers towards teaching sexuality education at a rate of (62.80%). The results also showed that there are statistically significant differences between the study results of females. And there were no significant differences in the teachers' attitudes due to the variable of experience, family status, and school subject. The results also emphasized the necessity of teaching sex education integrated with other subjects related to it, and it should be taught during adolescence, and they considered the role of the school as complementary to the role of the family in teaching this type of education.

(Levin & Hammock, 2020) conducted a study aimed at uncovering sex education in secondary schools in Canada. A sample of high school students in Canada, numbering (1845) students in high schools in Ontario, Canada, was selected, the sex education scale was applied to them that they received in school. The students' perspectives survey results revealed that most of the sexual education content, knowledge, and information was received in comprehensive sexuality education programs. Safety-based programs provided the most information about biology and relationships, as well as information on sexual violence. The results also show that the school context influences the amounts of information received about biology, relationships, and sexual violence, and all the important topics that potentially contribute to adolescents' sexual health and safety as they are.

The study (Lyu, Shen & Hesketh, 2020) aimed to explore gender differences in sexual knowledge, sexual attitudes, and sexual behaviors, as well as sexual education preferences among undergraduates in China. Where a cross-sectional study included (5965) students in universities (62.8% females), ranging in age from (15-24) years from nine universities in Zhejiang, Henan, and Yunnan provinces in China and the results revealed that the total sample was 158 (2.6%) identified 287 (4.8%) themselves as homosexual, 5.4) 324 stated that they were not clear about their gender identity. The degree of sexual knowledge was moderate, and sexual intercourse was previously reported by 18.7% (27.0% males and 13.9% females). And students from urban backgrounds and with homosexual and bisexual orientations were more likely to have sexual intercourse. Most students (72.5%) reported that they prefer receiving sex education from online sources, and female students were significantly more conservative in sexual attitudes and behaviors.

(Maziarz, Dake, Glassman & Mches, 2020) Conducted a study intended to reveal the nature of sex education offered in American high schools. A sample consisted of (297) principals from high school principals in the West, Northeast, Midwest, and South regions. The data results revealed that most regions teach comprehensive sexuality education (63%), which indicates the interest of schools in teaching students the concepts of sex education.

Studies of sexual harassment awareness

Al-Jubaila and Al-Tarif (2017) conducted a study aimed at identifying the problem of child sexual harassment: causes, effects, and treatment, by getting to know the nature of child sexual harassment cases and knowing the most prevalent types of child sexual harassment from the viewpoint of female specialists, the study also aims to identify the psychological and social causes of child molestation, the study sample consisted of (276) Saudi psychologists and social workers working in government hospitals in three regions in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, which are the regions (Eastern, Western, and Central). Data were collected by means of a questionnaire. The study found the following results: Children are more susceptible to sexual harassment extending their age (4-9) years, and females are more susceptible to sexual harassment than males, and most of the children's sex offenders are relatives, and the home of a relative or friend is one of the places where a child is most exposed to harassment. The study also found several psychological and social causes of child molestation. And the psychological and social effects resulting from sexual harassment on the abused child.

Badr El-Din (2019) conducted a study aimed at identifying the existing psychological structure behind the crime of sexual harassment, as well as identifying the personality type and its precise dynamic drivers, and the study sample consisted of (100) students who were divided into (50) females and (50) males whose ages range from (18-25). For this study, the multifaceted personality test was used to measure each trait separately, which is (Moral disorders - psychopathic - aggressive - psychotic) in addition to using the Eizenq Personality List to measure the neurotic trait, the self-esteem test translated and prepared by Ahmed Abdel Khaleq, the Rasmussen Self-Identity Scale, translated by Abdullah Falah Al-Manisel, and a test to measure the basic phenomenon of the study, which is sexual harassment, prepared by the researcher, and The results showed that there was no significant correlational relationship between male scores in some psychological traits and their scores in harassment, in addition to a positive and statistically significant correlation between female scores in a trait (psychopathy - aggressiveness - psychosis - self-esteem - immoral/neurotic disorders/identity crisis). And their scores in sexual harassment, in addition to the presence of statistically significant differences between the mean scores of females and males in (psychopathy - psychosis - aggression), while there are no differences between females and males in immoral disorders - self-esteem - neuroticism - identity crisis), and there are statistically significant differences between the average scores of females and males in sexual harassment in favor of males. In contrast, sexual harassment in males and females can be predicted through their scores in some psychological characteristics, the predictive ability of male sexual harassment is neuroticism, and the predictive ability of female sexual harassment is aggression.

(Rodríguez, Osuna, Dios & Amor, 2020) Conducted a study to reveal the students' level of knowledge of sexual harassment based on gender and students' beliefs about risk situations. A sample consisted of (268) male and female social sciences students at the University of Cordoba in Spain. A questionnaire was applied to perceptions and knowledge about sexual harassment. The results indicated that females were more aware of sexual harassment than males, and the participants expressed great awareness of sexual harassment, especially attitudes of jealousy, verbal harassment, and control over activities and relationships with other people.

The study (Jamshed & Kamal, 2020) aimed to find out the differences between the sexes and the prevalence of students' attribution of responsibility for sexual harassment; the study sample consisted of (500) university students, the number of which was (204) male, and (296) female students enrolled in two public universities, Qaid Azzam University and the University of Agriculture, and two private universities in Pakistan and a sexual knowledge questionnaire was applied to them. The results revealed that (78%) of the sample members gave women the responsibility for sexual harassment, while only (22%) stated that men are responsible for sexual harassment. The results revealed a high rate of sexual harassment towards women, and men blamed the women for sexual harassment.

The study (Kantha & Matsui, 2021) aimed to reveal the degree of awareness of undergraduate students in Japan about sexual harassment. A sample consisted of (90) male and female undergraduate students in Japan aged between (18-20) years were selected. A questionnaire of awareness of sexual harassment was distributed to the study sample by asking a group of questions to find out the extent of their awareness of sexual harassment, and the results showed that there is a blurry understanding of sexual harassment, which indicates a low level of awareness of sexual harassment, and the absence of differences between males and females in Degree of awareness of sexual harassment.

Sexual education and sexual harassment

Al-Hazmi's study (2019) aimed to uncover the role of parents to educate their children against exposure to sexual abuse, according to the variables of the family's socio-economic level. The research sample consisted of a random sample totaling (428) individuals from families in Makkah Al-Mukarramah who have children in the elementary stage. The results showed that parents' role in educating their children from exposure to sexual abuse according to the variables of the family's socio-economic level and that mothers' role in educating children about exposure to sexual abuse was greater than that of fathers. In addition to married fathers, people of (40) age and over, and the duration of their marriage (10) years or more, those with a higher education level,

government workers, high-income people, and the number of family members less than (4) individuals whose role was greater in Educate children against exposure to sexual abuse. And it was also evident that there was a direct correlation between the parents' role in educating children against exposure to sexual abuse and the parent's educational level, age, professional level, duration of the marriage, and the family's monthly income, while there is no correlation between gender, marital status, and the number of family members, and the questionnaire of the role of parents in educating children from exposure to sexual abuse. The study also found that parents' educational level was one of the most influencing factors on parents' role in educating their children from exposure to sexual abuse, followed by age, profession, and finally, the duration of the marriage.

Commenting on previous studies

In light of the review of previous studies that dealt with sex education and the degree of awareness of sexual harassment, the researcher found many studies that dealt with sex education and sexual harassment. Still, the studies did not examine each variable separately, and among the studies that dealt with sex education are the Gamrah study (2013), the Naqib study (2017), the Asiri and Badoud study (2017), the Gharib and Ibn Shanna study (2018), the Levin & Hammock study, (2020), and the Lyu, Shen & Hesketh study (2020), and Maziarz, Dake, Glassman & Mches (2020) study. Some studies have investigated sexual harassment independently in Arab and foreign environments and on various samples, primary, secondary, and university stages, such as the Badr al-Din study (2019), the (Rodríguez, Osuna, Dios & Amor, 2020) study, the (Jamshed & Kamal, 2020) study, and the study (Kantha & Matsui, 2021). And the closest study to the researcher's current study was the study of Al-Hazmi (2019), which dealt with parents' role to educate their children about exposure to sexual abuse in a group of families with children in the elementary stage in the city of Makkah Al-Mukarramah. Therefore, the current study was distinguished from previous studies in that it is the only study among previous studies in this field that followed the predictive methodology to find out the predictive power of sexual education in the awareness of their children, students, of sexual harassment, it was also one of the few studies conducted on students of the higher basic stage in the Jordanian environment. The researcher benefited from previous studies in reviewing the theoretical frameworks of sexual education and sexual harassment, developing the two standards of the study, justifying conducting the current study, and discussing the results in light of comparing his results with those of that study.

Study Methodology

The descriptive, predictive approach was followed, which is based on describing the reality of sexual education by parents and the students' awareness of sexual harassment and then studying the predictive power of sexual education practiced by parents in their students' children's awareness of sexual harassment.

Study Population

The study population consisted of students of the upper basic stage in government schools represented in grades (eighth, ninth, and tenth) in the Education Directorate of the University Brigade of the Amman Governorate in Jordan, and their number (13628) students. The number of eighth-grade students was (4870) male and female students, the number of ninth-grade students was (4549) male and female students, and the number of tenth-grade students was (4182) male and female students, as it was applied electronically in the second semester of the academic year (2020/2021 AD), and the table (2) shows the distribution of the members of the study population.

Table 1: Distribution of the study population of the higher basic stage students in the University District Education Directorate in the Amman Governorate in Jordan according to the grade and gender variables

Class	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
Eighth	2070	2800	4870
Ninth	2299	2250	4549
Tenth	2000	2182	4182
Total	6369	7232	13601

The Study Sample

From the eighth, ninth, and tenth grades in the Education Directorate of the University District in Amman Governorate, Jordan, and the method of selecting the sample was the available sample, and the method of electronic application was through an electronic link that was distributed to the students through social media. As the researcher could not direct application and visit schools due to the epidemiological situation due to the Coronavirus that has swept the country, and Table (2) shows the distribution of the study sample individuals.

Table 2: Distribution of the study sample of students of the higher basic stage in the Directorate of Education of the University District in Amman Governorate in Jordan according to the grade and gender variables

Variable	Variable level	Repetition	Percentage
Class	Eighth	129	34.5
	Ninth	125	33.4
	Tenth	120	32.1
	Total	374	100.0
Gender	Male	166	44.4
	Female	208	55.6
	Total	374	100.0

Study Tools

Two tools were developed to achieve the objectives of the current study, namely: the Sex Education Scale and the Sexual Harassment Awareness Scale, and they are as follows:

Sex Education Scale

The researcher developed the sex education scale after referring to the theoretical literature and previous studies in this field, such as Abdullah's study (2007), Gamrah study (2013), Al-Naqib study (2017), Asiri and Badoud study (2017), Gharib and Ibn Shanna study (2018), Levin & Hammock study (2020), Lyu, Shen & Hesketh study (2020), Maziarz, Dake, Glassman & Mches study (2020). Where the scale included in its initial form (30) items that measure the total degree of sexual education practiced by parents on their children from the students' viewpoint. To ensure the sex education scale's validity, it was presented to (10) referees specialized in educational psychology, measurement, and evaluation, and after placing their notes and suggestions on the scale. In light of the amendments that have been made, the scale has become composed of (28) items that measure the overall degree of sexuality education, and all Item s have been written in a positive direction, and there are no negative Item s.

To verify the indicators of building validity, an exploratory sample was chosen in the available method, consisting of (45) male and female students from the eighth, ninth, and tenth grades in the Education Directorate of the University District in Amman. They are not the sample of the study, then calculate the correlation coefficients between the Item s and the total score of the scale, as it was found that all the Item s have statistically significant correlation coefficients, which are as follows:

Table 3: Correlation coefficient between the Item and the total degree of the sex education scale

Item	Correlation coefficients	Item	Correlation coefficients	Item	Correlation coefficients
1	.522**	11	.523**	21	.459**
2	.476**	12	.510**	22	.586**
3	.780**	13	.633**	23	.494**
4	.397**	14	.587**	24	.567**
5	.776**	15	.674**	25	.592**
6	.528**	16	.313*	26	.685**
7	.535**	17	.477**	27	.327*
8	.520**	18	.617**	28	.346*
9	.710**	19	.351*		
10	.513**	20	.559**		

* Significant at the significance level (0.05)

** Significant at the significance level (0.01)

To achieve the reliability of the sex education scale, an exploratory sample was chosen in the available method, consisting of (45) male and female students from the eighth, ninth, and tenth grades in the Education Directorate of the University District in Amman, and they are not the study sample, then they were re-applied to them a second time after (14) days, and the Test-Retest calculated the reliability stability by computing the Pearson correlation coefficient, where the Test-Retest reached (0.927). The stability was calculated on the tribal scale using the Cronbach (alpha) equation for internal consistency, whereas, the stability of the total Cronbach alpha reached (0.835).

Sexual Harassment Awareness Scale

The researcher developed a scale of awareness of sexual harassment after returning to the theoretical literature and previous studies in this field, such as the study of Badr al-Din (2019), the study (Rodríguez, Osuna, Dios & Amor, 2020), the study (Jamshed & Kamal, 2020), and the study (Kantha & Matsui, 2021). The study closest to the researcher's current study was Al-Hazmi's (2019) study, as the scale included in its initial form (32) items distributed on four dimensions: sexual harassment, moral harassment, physical harassment, and laws relating to the punishment of sexual harassment. To ensure the validity of the awareness scale of sexual harassment, it was presented to (10) referees specialized in educational psychology, psychological counseling, measurement, and evaluation, and after placing their observations and suggestions on the scale, the most important of which were: Deleting three Items, to repeat their contents in other Items, and making some amendments to the language wording of the Items. In light of the amendments that have been made, the scale has become composed of (29) items divided into four dimensions, which are: Awareness of sexual harassment and its Items (1-8), awareness of moral harassment and its Items (9-17), awareness of physical harassment and its Items (18-24), and legal awareness of the punishment for sexual harassment and its Items (25-29). The scale Items were formulated in the positive direction, except (8) Items, namely: (5, 16, 22, 23, 24, 26, 27, 29), which were formulated in the negative direction, and reflected when performing the statistical analysis of the data. To verify the indicators of building validity, an exploratory sample was chosen in the available method, consisting of (45) male and female students from the eighth, ninth, and tenth grades in the Education Directorate of the University District in Amman. They are not the study sample, then calculate the correlation coefficients between the Items and the total score of the scale, as it was found that all the Items have statistically significant correlation coefficients, which are as follows:

Table 4: Correlation Coefficient between the Item and the total degree of the scale of the concepts of sexual harassment

Awareness of verbal harassment			Awareness of moral harassment			Awareness of physical harassment			Legal awareness of the penalty for sexual harassment		
Item	With dimension	With the total score	Item	With dimension	With the total score	Item	With dimension	With the total score	Item	With dimension	With the total score
1	.900**	.640**	9	.727**	.376*	18	.644**	.509**	25	.919**	.478**
2	.599**	.371*	10	.439**	.406**	19	.804**	.444**	26	.911**	.488**
3	.603**	.410**	11	.560**	.442**	20	.699**	.478**	27	.714**	.483**
4	.743**	.534**	12	.489**	.600**	21	.801**	.425**	28	.782**	.463**
5	.705**	.785**	13	.585**	.560**	22	.451**	.659**	29	.580**	.586**
6	.538**	.415**	14	.511**	.341*	23	.881**	.469**			
7	.903**	.674**	15	.653**	.367*	24	.612**	.327*			
8	.458**	.415**	16	.587**	.307*						
			17	.581**	.423**						

* Significant at the significance level (0.05)

** Significant at the significance level (0.01)

In order to achieve the reliability of the sex education scale, an exploratory sample was chosen in the available method, consisting of (45) male and female students from the eighth, ninth, and tenth grades in the Education Directorate of the University District in Amman, and they are not the study sample, then they were re-applied to them again after (14) days, and the Test-Retest calculated the reliability stability by computing the Pearson correlation coefficient, where the total repetition constant reached (0.908), and the reliability was also calculated on the pre-scale using the Cronbach (alpha) equation for internal consistency, where the overall Cronbach alpha stability reached (0.871). The following table shows the reliability ratios.

Table 5: Repetition reliability Coefficients and Stability of Internal Consistency, Cronbach Alpha for Domains and Overall Score of the Sexual Harassment Awareness Scale

Scale dimensions	Test/retest reliability	Internal consistency
Awareness of verbal harassment	0.881	0.833
Awareness of moral harassment	0.831	0.740
Awareness of physical harassment	0.854	0.827
Legal awareness of the penalty for sexual harassment	930.8	0.842
Total reliability	0.908	0.871

Key to correct the two scales:

A binary ranking was developed to answer the two scales' Items, where the ranking ranges between the following: Disagree (1) one degree and agree (2) two degrees, and higher scores describe trends of a high level of sexual education/awareness of sexual harassment, while the low scores close to the lower grades describe a low level of sex education/awareness of sexual harassment, and the performance was divided on the two scales into three levels according to the range of the category that ranges between (1-2), which are as follows:

- Averages between (1 - 1.33) indicate low-level sexual education/awareness of sexual harassment.
- Averages ranging between (1.34 - 1.67) indicate the intermediate level of sexual education/awareness of sexual harassment.
- Averages between (1.68 - 2) indicate a high level of sexual education/awareness of sexual harassment.

Study Variables

The study included the following variables:

- The level of sex education and has three levels: (low, medium, and high).
- The level of awareness of sexual harassment and has three levels: (low, medium, and high).

Statistical Methods

The following statistical methods were used:

- To answer the first and third questions, arithmetic means and standard deviations were used.
- A t-test was used to detect differences between two independent samples to answer the second and fourth questions.
- To answer the fifth question, multiple regression analysis was used.

Study Results and its Discussion

The following is a review of the results that were reached, as follows:

The results of the first question and its discussion, which reads: "What is the level of sexual education practiced by parents on their children, students of the higher primary stage in the governorate of the capital, Amman?"

To answer this question, arithmetic averages and standard deviations were calculated for the level of sexual education practiced by parents on their children, students of the higher basic stage in the capital Amman governorate, and Table (6) illustrates this.

Table 6: The arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the level of sexual education practiced by parents on their children, students of the higher basic stage in the university district in the capital Amman governorate, arranged in descending order according to the arithmetic averages

Rank	Number	Field	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Level
1.	4	My parents taught me modesty and a modest outlook on others.	1.86	.346	High
2.	2	I was raised to respect the opposite sex.	1.81	.391	High
3.	5	I was raised not to molest the opposite sex.	1.79	.407	High
4.	19	In the house, we have a boys 'bedroom and a girls' bedroom.	1.78	.414	High
5.	1	My parents assure me that no one can touch the "sexual" sensitive parts of my body.	1.76	.428	High
6.	13	My parents assure me that if I am ever being harassed or touching parts of my body, I must tell them immediately.	1.76	.430	High
7.	11	My parents assure me that there are body parts that are private that should not be encroached upon or just touched by others.	1.70	.459	High
8.	12	My parents taught me not to take off my clothes in front of anyone.	1.68	.468	High

Rank	Number	Field	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Level
9.	8	My parents tell me that males and females have similar body parts and also have some differences.	1.67	.471	Average
10.	7	My parents explain to me how to have children in married life.	1.64	.481	Average
11.	20	My parents forbid me to dress indecently, which is against customs, traditions, and religion.	1.64	.482	Average
12.	10	My parents taught me to tell them if I am asked to do something wrong.	1.63	.483	Average
13.	6	My parents talk to me about puberty and the changes that happen at that age.	1.55	.498	Average
14.	14	My parents told me that children could be sexually assaulted, either by close relatives or strangers.	1.55	.498	Average
15.	15	My parents taught me permission when entering someone's room.	1.51	.501	Average
16.	21	My parents taught me how to sit so that my nakedness was not visible.	1.48	.500	Average
17.	18	My parents answer my sexual questions.	1.41	.493	Average
18.	9	My parents told me that both males and females have reproductive organs that enable them to conceive.	1.40	.491	Average
19.	25	My parents taught me to run away or scream and seek help if I experience sexual harassment.	1.38	.486	Average
20.	22	My parents talk to me about stories of sexual assault and how people can defend themselves.	1.36	.480	Average
21.	26	My parents talk to me about issues of love and marriage.	1.36	.481	Average
22.	23	My parents taught me to distinguish between normal and abnormal contact from others.	1.32	.466	Low
23.	24	My parents taught me to be wary of over-praising my body from someone else.	1.32	.467	Low
24.	27	My parents listen to me about my emotional problems and offer me solutions.	1.30	.459	Low
25.	28	My parents get to know my friends and pay attention to any new friends.	1.30	.461	Low
26.	16	I was raised to comfortably talk to my parents about any sexual topic I'm exposed to.	1.20	.399	Low
27.	17	My parents provide an atmosphere of intimacy and reassurance when I talk to them about sexual education.	1.20	.399	Low
28.	3	My parents alerted me to the purpose of courtship for people older than me.	1.08	.276	Low
The total degree of sex education			1.52	.141	Average

Table (6) shows that the level of sexual education practiced by parents on their children, students of the higher basic stage in the capital Amman governorate, was average, as the arithmetic average of the total score was (1.52) with a standard deviation (0.141). This result indicates parental directives from the father and mother to their children regarding sexual issues. Still, it did not reach the high level, which is due to the presence of sexual issues and sensitive topics that parents are reluctant to bring up in front of their children. Parents leave the learning of some sexual concepts and knowledge to school because they are embarrassed about raising them in front of their children, or that they see that this age group does not need sexual education because they become adults and have sufficient knowledge about all sexual issues, they differ from young children who ask about everything without embarrassment or fear.

Item (2) which states: "My parents taught me modesty view of others" in the first rank between Item s with an arithmetic average (1.86) and a standard deviation (346.), and its level is high, and Item (4) which states: "I was raised to respect the opposite sex" ranked second with an arithmetic average (1.81) and a standard deviation (0.391), and its level is high, and perhaps the reason for this is that the Jordanian society is a conservative society that cares about raising children in the original Arab customs and traditions, and shyness is considered the essence and attributes of masculinity for the male. And an attribute that raises the status of

women in society, so parents are interested in raising children to live and look modestly, whether by male or female; moreover, the Islamic religion considers these qualities one of the characteristics of faith, and that modesty and decency, and respect for the opposite sex is part of the perfection of faith and obedience to God Almighty, and whoever does otherwise will be subjected to divine punishment. Parents also do not feel embarrassed to talk to their children about adherence to modesty, and these may be the reasons that made the second and fourth Items first in sexual education by parents for their children.

Item (16 and 17) were ranked next to last, and their texts, respectively: "I was raised to talk comfortably with my parents about any sexual topic I am exposed to," and "My parents provide an atmosphere of intimacy and reassurance when I talk to them about sexual education." And their average was (1.20) and their level was low, and this may be due to the parents' embarrassment of discussing these topics with their children, and for fear of parents that ask their children embarrassing questions, which require an answer and a deep explanation, so parents try not to provide an atmosphere of reassurance in raising these issues. Item (3) comes in the last rank, which states: "My parents alert me to the purpose of the courtship of people older than me," with arithmetic average (1.08) and a standard deviation (0.276), and its level is low, and the reason for this may be due to the nature of the study sample, where they are from the category of adult adolescents, and society and parents view them as adults, and they have awareness and knowledge that keeps parents away from alerting them to ways of wooing adults who are younger than them, as parents may consider their children old and know such tricks, and parents may think that adults' courtship is usually for younger age groups. Therefore, parents warn their children less about these issues.

The results of the study are in agreement with the results of the study (Maziarz, Dake, Glassman & Mches, 2020), which revealed that students receive sexual education at home and school and that there is interest in sex education; the results of the current study in this question differed with the results of the study of Asiri and Badoud (2017), in which the results indicated that fathers and mothers have positive trends towards their introduction of sexual education for their children at home, and Al-Hazmi (2019) study, which found the role of parents to educate their children from exposure to sexual abuse, according to the variables of the socio-economic level of the family. It disagreed with the study results (Lyu, Shen & Hesketh, 2020), whose results indicated that most students prefer to receive sex education from online sources.

The results of the second question and its discussion, and its text: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the level of sexual education practiced by parents on their children, students of the higher primary stage in the governorate of the capital, Amman, due to the variable of the gender of the children?

To answer this question, a t-test was used for two independent samples to find out the differences in the level of sexual education practiced by parents on their children, students of the higher basic stage in the Amman Governorate, according to the gender variable (male/female), and Table (7) illustrates Results.

Table 7: Results of the (t-test) test to find out the differences in the level of sexual education practiced by parents on their children, students of the higher basic stage in the Amman Governorate, according to the gender variable (male/female)

Variable	Variable level	Number	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	T value	Degrees of freedom	Statistical significance
Gender	Male	166	1.50	.137	2.407-	372	.017
	Female	208	1.53	.143			

Table (7) shows that there are statistically significant differences in the level of sexual education practiced by parents on their children, students of the higher basic stage in the capital Amman governorate according to the gender variable (male/female), where the value of (T) was (-2.407), and its statistical significance (0.017), which is statistically significant at the level of significance (0.05). The differences came in favor of females, as their arithmetic mean higher than males' average. And this indicates that sex education is practiced on girls more than males. The reason for this result may be due to the nature and specificity of the female in Arab society and the female's need for more sex education to preserve it and raise her level of awareness of sexual issues so that she is not exposed to any embarrassment and harassment, the reason for this result may also be due to the nature of the mother's relationship with the daughter and the absence of barriers between her and the girl, especially in sexual issues. The girl's need to know these issues, especially at the beginning of adolescence, and her need for education by the mother, which usually does not happen much between children and their father, So the differences came in favor of females.

The result of this question is in agreement with the results of the study of Gharib and Ibn Shanna (2018), where the results showed statistically significant differences in sex education between the genders in

favor of females, and the researcher did not find anything that differs with the results of the current study.

The results of the third question and its discussion, which states: “What is the level of awareness of sexual harassment among students of the upper primary stage in the capital, Amman?”

To answer this question, arithmetic averages and standard deviations were calculated for the degree of awareness of sexual harassment among students of the higher basic stage in the capital Amman Governorate, and Table (8) illustrates this.

Table 8: The arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the degree of awareness of sexual harassment among students of the higher basic stage in the capital Amman governorate, arranged in descending order according to the arithmetic averages

Rank	Number	Dimension	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Level
1.	1	Awareness of verbal sexual harassment	1.58	.182	Average
2.	2	Awareness of moral sexual harassment	1.57	.244	Average
3.	3	Awareness of physical, sexual harassment	1.56	.272	Average
4.	4	Legal awareness of sexual harassment	1.52	.221	Average
The overall degree of awareness of sexual harassment			1.56	.140	Average

Table (8) shows that the degree of awareness of sexual harassment among students of the upper primary stage in the governorate of the capital, Amman, was average, as the arithmetic means of the total score was (1.56) with a standard deviation (0.140), and the "awareness of verbal sexual harassment" came first with arithmetic mean (1.58) with a standard deviation (0.182), while the dimension "legal awareness of sexual harassment" came last with an average (1.52) and a standard deviation (0.221). This result indicates that students have a good degree of awareness of sexual harassment, but this degree is not sufficient as it did not reach the high level, and this indicates that students are ignorant of some issues related to sexual harassment, and the reason for this may be due to social embarrassment in raising these issues. And the presence of a barrier between parents and children in raising sexual issues, and the failure to provide an atmosphere of reassurance, familiarity, and comfort in discussing these topics with children, and the reliance of children on unknown sources in forming a system of concepts related to sexual harassment, which leads to confusion and ambiguity in some concepts and issues related to sexual harassment.

The result indicated that legal awareness of sexual harassment was ranked last, and this is an indication that students miss some of the facts and legal issues related to sexual harassment, and this is due to the low levels of social, informational, educational, and family education for legal issues related to sexual issues. The reason may be an embarrassment in raising these topics or taking the school lessons that are presented in the school, especially in biology, social education, and Islamic education subjects to the light of mockery and ridicule by the students, and their failure to study them seriously and with interest. This question's result is in agreement with the results of the study (Rodríguez, Osuna, Dios & Amor, 2020), where the study participants expressed a great awareness of sexual harassment.

The results of this question differed from the results of the study by Kantha & Matsui (2021), where it was found from its results that there is a blurry understanding of the students' understanding of sexual harassment, which indicates a low level of awareness of the concepts of sexual harassment.

The results of the fourth question and its discussion, and its text: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the degree of awareness of sexual harassment among students of the upper primary stage in the governorate of the capital, Amman, due to the variable of children's sex?

To answer this question, a t-test was used for two independent samples to find out the differences in the degree of awareness of sexual harassment among students of the higher basic stage in the capital Amman governorate according to the gender variable (male/female) and Table (9) illustrates the results.

Table 9: Results of the (t-test) to find out the differences in the degree of awareness of sexual harassment among students of the higher basic stage in the capital Amman Governorate according to the gender variable (male/female)

Variable	Variable level	Number	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	T value	Degrees of freedom	Statistical significance
Gender	Male	166	1.57	.138	1.044	372	.297

	Female	208	1.55	.141			
--	--------	-----	------	------	--	--	--

Table (9) shows that there are statistically significant differences in the degree of awareness of sexual harassment among students of the higher basic stage in the capital, Amman, according to the gender variable (male/female), where the value of (T) is (1.044). Its statistical significance is (0.297), and it is not statistically significant at the level of significance (0.05), and this indicates that the degree of awareness of sexual harassment is similar for males and females, and this may be because parents' interest in girls' sexual education has led to their increased awareness of sexual harassment so that the degree between them and males is close. The reason for this may also be due to the nature of social and media openness, ease of access to information from Internet sites, the spread of news of harassment, methods, and types of harassment through social media, and informing both males and females about the news of harassment, which led males and females to agree on the degree of awareness of sexual harassment. And the result of this question is in agreement with the results of the study (Kantha & Matsui, 2021), as its results revealed that there are no differences between males and females in the degree of awareness of sexual harassment, and the researcher did not find anything that differs with the results of the current study.

The fifth question results and its discussion, which reads: "What is the degree of prediction of sexual education practiced by parents on the awareness of higher primary stage students in Jordan of sexual harassment?"

To answer this question and determine the extent to which sex education contributes to predicting the degree of awareness of sexual harassment, a sample regression analysis was used according to the total method (Enter), and Table (8) illustrates that:

Table 8: Results of simple regression analysis to determine the extent to which sex education contributes to predicting the degree of awareness of sexual harassment

Dependent variable	Explained predictive variables	The R correlation	R2 coefficient of determination	F value	F statistical significance	Beta value	T value	T Statistical significance
Degree of awareness of sexual harassment	Sex education	0.765	0.586	523.54	.000	.765	22.881	.000

Predictor (constant variable): sex education

The predictor (dependent variable): awareness of sexual harassment.

The results of Table (8) revealed that the value of the correlation (R) between sex education and the degree of awareness of sexual harassment amounted to (0.765), the determination factor (R2) reached (0.586), and the determination coefficient (R2) indicates the percentage of sexual education interpretation or prediction of the degree of awareness of sexual harassment, that is, it explains the rate (58.6%) of the change in awareness of sexual harassment among students of the upper basic stage in Amman, and the value of (F) was (523.54) and its statistical significance (0.000), which is statistically significant. The results also showed that the contribution of sex education in predicting the degrees of awareness of sexual harassment among students was high and statistically significant, as the value of (t) was (22.881), and in statistical terms (0.000), and the value of Beta was (0.765), which expresses the percentage of sexual education's contribution to explaining or predicting the degree of awareness of sexual harassment among students. This result indicates that the parenting practices followed with their children in raising them and directing them towards sexual issues, and providing an atmosphere of familiarity, love and reassurance in raising such issues, leads to an increase in students' awareness of sexual harassment, and this is because a sound cognitive foundation leads to a heightened awareness of such issues, and knowledge of their concepts, when parents provide positive parenting practices in their upbringing, and provide a nurturing, supportive, and safe environment to raise different sexual issues, and they accept all the questions of their children without offense, sarcasm or oppression, as this leads to a constructive dialogue between the two parties in these issues, and directs the children towards good practices, and knowing the information from its sound and safe source, neither the son nor the girl resort to other methods to find answers to the questions on their minds, which may be wrong or perverted answers in many cases. The results of this question agree with the results of the study of Al-Hazmi (2019), which concluded the role of parents to educate their children from exposure to sexual abuse, according to the variables of the social and economic level of the family.

Study Recommendations

In light of the results of the current study, the researcher recommends the following:

- Providing informational and educational programs specialized in sexual education and sexual harassment, targeting different age groups, especially the adolescent period.
- Incorporate the topics of sexual education and sexual harassment into school curricula, present them interestingly and attractively, and answer the questions that occur to any student or teenager.
- Directing teachers to pay attention and seriousness when introducing sexuality education issues in school curricula.
- Conducting training programs for parents and families on issues related to sexual education and how to deal with children when raising issues of sexual education and sexual harassment.
- Conducting various studies on the variables related to sexual education and sexual harassment among different students' samples within different age stages.

References

- Abu Riach, H. (2006). Abuse and gender. Amman: Dar Al Fikr Publishers and Distributors.
- Al-Jubaila, Al-Jawhara and Al-Turaif, G. (2017). Causes, effects, and remedies of sexual harassment of children: A sociological, psychological study. *King Khalid University Journal for the Humanities*, 26, (2), 167-191.
- Al Hazmi, K. (2019). The role of parents in educating children against exposure to sexual abuse. *Journal of Arts, Literature, Humanities and Sociology*, Emirates College of Educational Sciences, No. (33), 268-282.
- Al sayid, Iman. (2000). Child sexual harassment: definition, causes, prevention, and treatment. Egypt: Dar Al Zahraa for Publishing and Distribution.
- Shaker, B. (2012). How to protect your child from sexual harassment? *Journal of Islamic Awareness*, Ministry of Endowments and Islamic Affairs, 50, (750), 72-75.
- Alshamas, I. (2003). Sex education in the family between concept and practice. *Journal of the Association of Arab Universities for Education and Psychology*, Damascus University, 1, (3), 98-134.
- Abdullah, A. (2007). Parents' attitudes towards sexuality education and their related educational practices in Amman. Unpublished MA thesis, University of Jordan, Amman, Jordan.
- Asiri, R. & Badoud, A. (2017). Parents' attitudes towards providing sexual education for their kindergarten children in Riyadh. *Reading and Knowledge Magazine*, Ain Shams University, No. (193) 59-86.
- Atta, I. & Eid, R. (2012). Sex education. The eleventh scientific conference entitled The Crisis of Values in Educational Institutions. Fayoum University, Fayoum, Egypt, May 2012 AD, 15 - 52.
- Gharib, S. (2010). Sexual harassment is a risk your child faces. Egypt: Al-Andalus Publishing and Distribution House.
- Gamrah, H. (2013). The relationship between a teenage girl and her mother and its implications for her sexual education. *Journal of Specific Education Research*, Mansoura University, Issue (31), 44-74.
- Alnaqib, I. (2017). Sex education in kindergarten institutions. *Journal of Studies in Childhood and Education*, Assiut University, Issue (2), 1-44.
- Al-Yamani, A. (2014). Social, emotional, and moral development in children. Amman: the author.
- Barbo, E. (2003). The Effects of Child Sexual Abuse, Child Physical Abuse, and Combined Child Sexual and Physical Abuse on Adult Sexual Victimization and Adult Posttraumatic Stress Disorder. Ph.D., Northern Illinois University. The United States.
- Dosdale, C & Skarparis, K. (2020). Supporting survivors of sexual violence and abuse during the COVID-19 pandemic. *British Journal of Nursing*, 29, (20), 1159 – 1163.
- Jamshed, N & Kamal, A. (2020) Gender differences in the attribution of responsibility for sexual harassment: A students' perspective. *JPMA. The Journal of the Pakistan Medical*, 70, (2), 341- 343.
- Jung, H & Yoon, H. (2020). How Does Sexual Harassment Influence the Female Employee's Negative Response in a Deluxe Hotel? *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17, (9537), 2- 13.
- Kantha, S & Matsui, Y. (2021). What Is Sexual Harassment? Perceptions of Japanese University Students. *International Medical Journal*, 28, (1), 86 – 89.
- Kristina. R (2009). Sexual Harassment Policies: Justice Perceptions and Intentions to Report. University of Houston: Umi Number: 3361439,1,64.
- Lyu, J., Shen, X & Hesketh, T. (2020). Sexual Knowledge, Attitudes and Behaviours among Undergraduate Students in China—Implications for Sex Education. *International journal of environmental research and public*. 17 (18),
- Rodríguez, M., Osuna, L., Dios, I & Amor, M. (2020). Perception of Gender-Based Violence and Sexual

- Harassment in University Students: Analysis of the Information Sources and Risk within a Relationship. International journal of environmental research and public health, 17, (3754), 2- 14.
- Sex Information & Education Council of Canada "SIECCAN". (2019). Canadian guidelines for sexual health education. Toronto, On: Sex Information & Education Council of Canada (SIECCAN). Retrieved from <http://sieccan.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/Canadian-Guidelines-for-Sexual-Health-Education.pdf>.
- UNESCO. (2009). International technical guidance on sexuality education: An evidence-informed approach for schools, teachers, and health educators. Retrieved from, <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0018/001832/183281e.pdf>.
- World Health Organization "WHO." (2017). Violence Against Women. 2017. <https://tinyurl.com/y8pgr4hx>.

Author Information

Dr. Abdul Raouf Hamid Al-Yamani
Associate Professor - Faculty of Educational
Sciences - Isra University - Department of Child
Education
